

Pant Dhan 6, a new variety for the hills of Uttar Pradesh

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The hilly region of Uttar Pradesh (about 46,485 km²) has diverse soil, topography, and rainfall. High-yielding varieties capable of performing well at lower and medium altitudes (up to 1,676 m) have been lacking.

Pant Dhan 6, a high-yielding variety recently released for this area, was evolved by the pedigree method following hybridization of IR8608-298-3-1 and IR10179-23 at IRRI. As IR19728-9-3-2, it was introduced in India through the 1981 International Rice Observational Nursery and grown at Pantnagar during the wet season.

Pant Dhan 6 is an early maturing (113-120 d in the hills), semidwarf variety suitable for transplanting at lower and medium altitudes. During 3 or testing, Pant Dhan 6 performed better than K39, Majhera 3, Thapachini, and other local checks

(Table 1). In the hill regions of Uttar Pradesh, it yielded 65% higher than standard variety K39 and 67% higher than local check Thapachini. It has medium slender grains.

Pant Dhan 6 has shown resistance

to leaf blast and brown leaf spot and moderate resistance to neck blast and leaf scald, the most common diseases in the hills. It has shown resistance to stem borer and moderate susceptibility to leafhoppers (Table 2). □

Table 1. Grain yield and days to flowering of Pant Dhan 6 in Uniform Variety Trials at Hawalbagh, Almora (U.P.), India, 1983-85.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)				Days to 50% flowering			
	1983	1984	1985	Mean	1983	1984	1985	Mean
Pant Dhan 6	2.9 ^a	4.2 ^a	5.2 ^a	4.1	91	81	92	88
K39	1.4	2.1	4.0	2.5	79	73	83	78
Thapachini (local check)	2.0	3.5	3.6	2.4	98	107	102	102
CD at 0.05	1162	1164	824					
CV (%)	22.5	24.5	11.6					

^aSignificantly superior to K39 and Thapachini.

Table 2. Reaction of 3 varieties to diseases and insects at Hawalbagh, Almora, India, 1983 kharif.

Variety	Reaction ^a					
	Disease				Insect	
	Neck blast	Leaf scald	Sheath rot	Brown leaf spot	Stem borer	Leafhopper
Pant Dhan 6	5	5	7	3	3	7
K39	9	5	5	3	7	7
Thapachini (local check)	5	7	7	4	5	7

^aStandard evaluation system for rice 0-9 scale.

Swarnaprabha, a physiologically efficient variety

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Ptb 43 or Swarnaprabha, an early high-yielding variety from the cross Bhavani/Triveni was released in Kerala State in Feb 1985. The new variety is suitable for all three growing seasons.

Swarnaprabha and 11 other promising early rice cultivars of similar duration (Ratna as check) were field tested in 2 dry (Dec-Apr 1985 and 1986) and 1 wet (Jun-Nov 1985) season trials at 15- × 10-cm spacing. Sixty kg N as urea was applied in 3 equal splits: at seeding, 20 d after seeding, and booting.

Agronomic characteristics of Swarnaprabha and check variety Ratna at Cuttack, India.

Character	1985 wet season		1985 dry season		1986 dry season	
	Swarnaprabha	Ratna	Swarnaprabha	Ratna	Swarnaprabha	Ratna
Duration (d)	117	122	130	135	130	135
Height (cm)	113	86	107	82	112	86
Panicles/m ²	313	370	387	478	389	430
Spikelets/m ² × 10 ³	27.4	22.1	28.5	25.1	33.9	30.2
Grains/m ² × 10 ³	21.1	15.8	23.1	18.9	26.8	24.5
1,000-grain weight (g)	24.5	21.7	23.7	19.8	25.2	21.8
Total dry matter (g/m ²)	1012	786	1218	967	1159	999
Grain yield (g/m ²)	465	325	499	409	644	531
Harvest index	46	41	41	42	56	53
Solar energy utilization (Eu %)	1.11	0.91	1.00	0.75	0.94	0.75
Crop growth rate (panicle initiation to flowering, g/m ² per d)	19.9	12.2	23.1	12.0	19.2	18.8
Crop growth rate (flowering to harvest, g/m ² per d)	10.7	9.9	18.3	18.0	12.5	6.5
Sink capacity (g/m ²)	671	480	678	497	855	659
Postflowering dry matter (g/m ²)	363	248	493	449	400	215

Duration was 120 d in the wet season and 130 d in the dry (see table).

Productive panicles/ m² were about 390 in the dry season and 310 in the

wet. It has medium bold grains (1,000-grain weight = 24.0 g) and white kernels. Height is 110 cm, with leaf area index about 3.5, harvest index 0.46, and solar energy utilization 1.11% in the wet and 0.94% in the dry seasons.

Swarnaprabha had the highest dry matter and grain yield in one wet and two dry seasons. Crop growth rate during reproductive and ripening stages, sink capacity, and postflowering dry matter accumulation were high, resulting in high spikelet

and grain numbers/m². Yields were over 4.5 and 5.5 t/ha in the wet and dry seasons.

Yield difference between seasons was marginal, showing its stability. □

Two upland rice varieties recommended for release in Nigeria

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To identify high-yielding and short-duration varieties for upland environments, five entries selected from local testing at Ibadan were evaluated in multilocational trials during the 1984 and 1985 wet seasons. IRAT133 and IRAT144 were the best performers (see table). They also had

Performance of IRAT133 and IRAT144 in upland environments in Nigeria.

Variety	Height (cm)	Days to flowering	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Increase (%) over check
IRAT144	127	75	3.0	43
IRAT133	116	72	2.9	38
ITA257 (check)	118	72	2.1	—

^aAv of 1984 and 1985 multilocational trials.

the highest yields in 1983 Ibadan trials. The Third National Conference of the Nationally Coordinated Research Project on Rice (Apr 1986) has recommended that they be released for cultivation.

IRAT133 and IRAT144 are crosses

of IRAT13 and IRAT10, introduced from Ivory Coast. They have short duration and disease and drought resistance. IRAT133 is short, IRAT144 is medium and has the better plant type. □

Two high-yielding varieties for southern Andhra Pradesh wet season

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NLR27999 and NLR9672-96 are semidwarf varieties with higher yield potentials than NLR9672 and NLR9674. Both have grain dormancy after harvest and yield as high as 6.5 t/ha in the wet season. Both yield well, even with 60-d-old seedlings. NLR27999 is suitable for late planting, up to the end of Oct.

NLR9672-96 is a secondary selection from NLR9672, derived from Bulk H-9/ Millek kuening. NLR27999 is a cross derivative of RP3 1-49-2/ BCPI. Bulk H-9 and BCPI are tall, Molagolukulu-grain type. Millek kuening and RP31-49-2 are resistant to blast (Bl).

Grains of NLR27999 and NLR9672-96 are short and bold with dirty brown

Table 1. Agronomic traits of NLR27999 and NLR9672-96 and pest and disease reactions. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Character	NLR27999	NLR9672-96	NLR9672	NLR9674
Duration (d)	160-170	150-160	150-160	160-170
Plant type	Semidwarf, compact tillering, nonlodging, light green foliage with erect flag leaf	Semidwarf, compact tillering, nonlodging, light green foliage with droopy flag leaf	Semidwarf, compact tillering, nonlodging, light green foliage with droopy flag leaf	Semidwarf, compact tillering, nonlodging, light green foliage with erect flag leaf
Plant height (cm)	113	119	100	104
Tillering ability	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
Panicles/m ²	289	282	248	269
Grains/panicle	291	301	339	326
1000-grain weight (g)	21.8	21.5	23.5	22.5
Dormancy	Present	Present	Present	Present
Reaction to Blast	Moderately resistant	Moderately resistant	Susceptible	Susceptible
Bacterial blight	Moderately resistant	Moderately resistant	Moderately resistant	Susceptible
Brown plant-hopper	Resistant	Resistant	Resistant	Resistant
Gall midge	Susceptible	Susceptible	Susceptible	Susceptible

glumes, similar to that of traditional Molagolukulu. Grain shedding at maturity is less than in NLR9672. Threshability is good. Milled rice is

white and translucent.

NLR9672-96 matures in 150-160 d and NLR27999 in 160-170 d. Both are weakly photoperiod sensitive and are